

DEVELOPMENT OF CLAY-POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES (PNC) FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION

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SUMMARY

Clay polymer nanocomposites have received much interest in various applications including packaging, transportation, electronic and construction. The layer structure of clay in which its thickness is in the range of a nanometer provides unique advantages over other nano-particles in reinforcing polymer matrices, such as stiffness and strength, barrier properties, and fire resistance. The key issues are to exfoliate the clay layers fully in the matrix and establish a good interface with the matrix. Different approaches from 1) chemistry to modify the clay surface and the polymer matrix to make them compatible with each other, to 2) processing equipment to disperse and exfoliate the clays well in the polymer matrix and 3) formulation to tailor the industry needs will be the main objectives of this presentation. Commercialisation and application of clay polymer nanocomposites in various key sectors will also be discussed.

Keywords: nanoclay, nanocomposite, thermoset, thermoplastic, performance.

INTRODUCTION

Fabrication of PNCs can be achieved by several ways. Melt compounding is the most practical and economical way for the formation of thermoplastic PNCs while in-situ polymerisation is the only possible way for thermoset PNCs. Depending on the compatibility between the matrix and the clays, different types of structure can be achieved including conventional composites, intercalated and exfoliated nanocomposites (Fig. 1). Among them the exfoliated structure is the most desirable because it ensures 1) a maximum aspect ratio thus a maximum reinforcing effect and 2) a greatest surface for the load transfer from the matrix to the nanoparticles. Although achieving the exfoliation structure is not always simple and it remains a great challenge for most hydrophobic polymer systems.

DEVELOPMENTS

The first approach inherited from the grease industry was the modification of clay surface using alkylamine compounds derived from fatty acid. This can reduce

significantly the hydrophilicity of the clay surface and also the interaction between the clay layers, thus increase the possibility of polymer molecules to diffuse into the clay galleries. This method works well for the more hydrophilic polymers like polyamides and polyesters but not the hydrophobic polyolefins and other thermosets like polyesters, vinylester, etc.

The second chemical approach is to modify the polymer matrices to make them more compatible with the clays by introducing functional groups on the polymer molecules, preferable at the chain ends, such as carboxylic acid, amine, hydroxyl, etc. This method has been widely used for hydrophobic polyolefins although the exfoliation issue cannot be fully solved and the cost involved poses some challenge.

Beside the chemical approaches, the mechanical approaches have also been developed by introducing different mechanical forces to exfoliate the clay layers. Shearing force is the most powerful tool for shearing clay layers apart from each other but it has a counter effect on the matrix. Elongational shear device is an example. Processing aids such as gas or vapor have also been used with special extruders to help the clay exfoliation but it is less attractive due to the complication of equipment and large energy involved.

APPLICATIONS

A number of industrial applications of PNCs have been put in place. The most attractive applications were aiming to improve the barrier properties of thermoplastic packaging. The layer structure of the clays modifies the permeation path of small gas molecules in the polymer films. Clay polyamide nanocomposites are the most successful materials for the packaging industry. These have been approved by the FDA for non-direct contact with food and one for direct contact with food.

As the concern of halogen compound on the environment is increasing, clays have been found as an interesting alternative flame retardant for several applications, especially in transportation, cables and electronic devices. Clays can be used alone or as a synergic component in the flame retardant.

Due their high strength and stiffness clays have also been used to improve the performance of thermoplastics, for example, the use of TPO in the automotive industries.

CONCLUSION

PNCs have been developed for some time and although there are some challenges put their application is on the rise.

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